

The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Job Satisfaction

Kamal Gautam

Department of Human Research, Career Point University, Kota

Email Id- kamalgautam23@gmail.com

Guide Name - Prof. (Dr.) Gurudatt Kakkar, Career Point University

Abstract

Emotional Intelligence is an important factor for teacher's success. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the impact of Emotional Intelligence on Job Satisfaction among the academicians in Technical higher education institutions. In the past, when studying organizational behavior, emotions and EQ were not given serious attention, especially on their contribution towards creativity and productivity. In the same light, limited attempts were also made in investigating the effect of EQ on work attitude and behavior such as job satisfaction and job commitment.

In aspects of gender and age females, by handling multiple responsibilities are comparatively more prone to high stress & an unbalanced lifestyle. The EQ level of females with special focus on age & marital status. In male are less stresses but unbalanced lifestyle.

Findings suggest that Emotional Intelligence did not affect the level of Job Satisfaction. Gender did not have a significant effect on Emotional Intelligence or Job Satisfaction. Older employees had higher levels of Emotional Intelligence; however, age had no effect on reported Job Satisfaction. Gender did not have a moderating effect in Emotional Intelligence-Job Satisfaction relationship. Age had mixed findings. For the younger generation, the relationship was significantly positive. For the older generation, it was insignificant and negative. Results should be approached with caution. Limitations and future research directions are provided in the article. Data collection is done on the basis of convenience sampling technique.

Researchers have acknowledged that job satisfaction is a phenomenon which can be explained as having both cognitive and affective character. The cognitive component is made up of judgments and beliefs about the job, while the affective component comprises of feelings and emotions associated with the job. Job satisfaction is defined as the attitude and feelings people have about their work: positive and favorable attitudes towards the job indicate job satisfaction while negative and unfavorable attitudes toward the job indicate job dissatisfaction.

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Key Words: Emotional intelligence, Job Satisfaction, Stress, Management, age, gender

Emotional intelligence:

Emotional intelligence (EI) as an inclusive theory was discussed in the work of psychologists (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). According to them, EI is an important component of social intelligence and it is the ability of an individual to understand and control their own thoughts and sentiments. In addition, they are also capable of using this intelligence in steering their actions. EI helps an individual to encourage self-feelings, to remain positive as well as nurture relationships. Research has highlighted the importance of EI in enhancing social interactions for teachers' success in educational institutions (Arani, 2011).

The literature suggests that EI also varies between men and women (Harrod & Scheer, 2005). As per their biological nature women are more intense and experience positive and negative emotions as compared to their male counterpart. From childhood, women are oriented to be emotional socially while men are taught to be strong and emotionally stable. Petrides and Furnham (2006) believe there are gender differences as each group experiences different responsibilities, life situations and stressors. Hence, in their study, they fixed the gender variable and focused on females only.

REVIEW OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE CONCEPT

Since 1980 new theories of intelligence have been introduced and are gradually replacing the traditional theory. The whole child has become the centre of education not only his reasoning capacities, but also his creativity, emotions, and interpersonal skills. The Multiple Intelligences theory has been introduced by Howard Gardner (1983), and the Emotional Intelligence theory by BarOn (1985), Mayer and Salovey (1990) and Goleman (1995). IQ alone is no more the measure for success; it only counts for 20%, and the rest goes for Emotional and Social Intelligences, and luck (Goleman, 1995).

Emotional Intelligence: It is being able to monitor our own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use this to guide our thinking and actions (Salovey and Mayer, 1990). The emotionally intelligent person is skilled in four areas: Identifying, using, understanding, and regulating emotions (Mayer and Salovey, 1993). According to Goleman (1995) emotional intelligence consists of five components: Knowing our emotions (self-awareness), managing them, motivating ourselves, recognizing emotions in others (empathy), and handling relationships.

Achievement: it is refers to the student ability and performance; it is multidimensional; it is intricately related to human growth and cognitive, emotional, social, and physical development; it reflects the whole child; it is not related to a single instance, but occurs across time and levels, through a student's life in public school and on into post-secondary

years and working life (Steinberger, 1993); and also achievement is the quality and quantity of a student's work. This second definition is the one that more or less applies to this research, the former being too exhaustive. What we need here is the quality of the students' work; we need to calculate the mean of their overall grades during the first semester of the current year.

EI and gender have a limited exposure in the scientific field (Mandell & Pherwani, 2003). In the study conducted by the same aforementioned authors, they found significant difference in the mean scores on EI between men and women. In a comparative study done by Shahzad and Bagum (2012), significant difference was found between males and females on Trait EI. In addition, unlike the default assumption, males scored a higher mean score than females on the overall EI.

Investigating the relationship between emotional and social competencies in relation to gender, Hopkins and Bilimoria (2008) conducted a study consisting of 105 top level executives in financial organizations. The results show that there were no significant differences between male and female leaders with regard to displaying emotional and social competencies. The results were different, however when it was conducted among youth. Harrod and Scheer (2005) investigated the relationship between EI and demographic characteristics (age, sex, household income, parents' level of education, and location of residence) among youths aging between 16-19 years old. Results have shown that EI levels were positively related to females, parents' education, and household income. Females have shown higher EI levels than males. Moreover, EI scores differed with age.

As per Karniz (2005) study, Emotional Intelligence also varies with age. When the survey was done at the age of ten, both genders reflected same emotions at extreme ends. Girls also showed anger like boys when they get annoyed. But when the study was done at the age of thirteen, the aggression in girls converted into passive form of reflection like backbiting, gossiping, negative grapevines and indirect revenge. Fariselli, Ghini and Freedman (2006) found a positive but weak relationship between age and EI. Their sample reported that age only predicted 1.6% of EI. The researchers recommended investigating other variables that may affect EI.

Several studies tested the interaction between EI, age and gender. Extremera, Fernandez and Salovey (2006) surveyed Spanish students. They found that females showed higher EI than males and that with aging, EI increases as well for both. Alumran and Punamaki (2008) tested the effect of EI on reaching adolescence in teenagers. They found that girls exhibit higher EI than boys. However, they did not find any age differences.

Singh and Srivastava (2012) investigated age and gender of managers and their effect on EI. Age affected EI in groups of up to 30 and 50-60 years old. However, gender did not have an impact. Gaitniece-Putane (2006) used the MANOVA test and found that age, gender and their interaction together influence EI, specifically dimensions of empathy and social responsibility. In addition, the age group 30-35 years old showed the highest scores on EI.

Some scales which effect the EI depending on person which can change the mind that is:-

A. Intrapersonal Scale

The subcomponents of the Intrapersonal EQ scale include Self-Regard, Emotional Self-Awareness, Assertiveness, Independence, and Self-Actualization. The responses to items on the Total Intrapersonal composite scale are indicative of an individual who has good self-understanding and who is achieving well up to this point in his life.

Self-Regard The responses indicate reasonable self-regard and an adequate degree of self-respect and self-confidence.

Emotional Self-Awareness The responses suggest highly effective emotional self-awareness and indicate an individual who knows how his feelings and emotions impact on his own opinions, attitudes, and judgments.

Assertiveness. The responses indicate a reasonably good ability to express thoughts, feelings, and emotions.

Independence. The responses indicate an individual who is independent in his thinking and who also has a strong preference to act independently. +

Self-Actualization. The results indicate an individual who feels reasonably content with his accomplishments and with his ongoing activities and roles.

B. Interpersonal Scale

This component of the Total EQ-i scale taps interpersonal capacity and functioning. The subcomponents of the Interpersonal scale include Empathy, Social Responsibility, and Interpersonal Relationship. Most interpersonal situations are handled well and with confidence. Most of the time, the opinions and attitudes of others are understood, and he has the ability to relate to people reasonably well. The score is reflective of someone who is usually responsible, dependable, and functions well in tasks involving making contact with others and cooperation.

Empathy. The responses indicate an individual who has a good awareness, understanding, and appreciation of the feelings of others most of the time.

Social Responsibility. The responses pertaining to the Social Responsibility scale indicate an individual who is cooperative and constructive. People who show social responsibility will be helpful when interacting with others and will actively contribute to the "community at large" (society, the corporation, team, etc.).

Interpersonal Relationship The responses portray an individual who has above average interpersonal skills. This is the scale that ties most directly to the ability to interact with others. Students who show abilities for interpersonal relationships are able to form agreeable relationships and alliances. This ability supports effective communication and the mutually beneficial exchanges of ideas, feelings, and information.

C. Adaptability Scales

This part of EQ-i is composed of the Reality Testing, Flexibility, and Problem Solving Scales and examines how successful one is in coping with environmental demands based on one's ability to effectively size up and deal with problematic situations. The Adaptability component is substantially higher than average.

Reality Testing. The results indicate an individual who has an enhanced ability to evaluate and grasp the correspondence between what he experiences (the "subjective") and the facts/reality (the "objective"). This type of person is often described as realistic, well grounded, and "tuned in" to what's going on around him/her. The results indicate a fairly typical ability to adjust emotions, thoughts, and behaviour in dynamic environments and changing conditions. Like most people, significant changes may be perceived as difficult, but most adjustments are handled adequately.

Flexibility. The results indicate a typical ability to adjust emotions, thoughts, and behaviour in dynamic environments and changing conditions.

Problem Solving The responses to this scale reflect an effective approach to resolving problems. Students who show some abilities to solve problems probably has a very deliberating style, and are good at defining problems as well as generating and implementing potentially effective solutions.

D. Stress Management Scale

The Stress Management component of EQ-i consists of the Stress Tolerance and Impulse Control Subscales. Both components of this composite scale are above average indicating a calm disposition, lack of impulsivity, and the ability to withstand stress.

Stress Tolerance The results of the Stress Tolerance scale indicate an enhanced ability to withstand adverse events and stressful situations. Students who show some stress tolerance are generally able to cope with stress actively and effectively. They are generally calm and rarely gets overly anxious or agitated even when under pressure.

Impulse Control The results indicate effective impulse control ability that suggests an individual who is able to resist or delay impulses, drives, and temptations to act. Students who show a reflexive thinking or control of their impulses are rarely impatient, rarely overreact, or lose control. Proper thought is given to decisions and actions helping to avoid careless or costly mistakes.

E. General Mood Scales

The subcomponents of this composite scale consist of the Optimism and Happiness subscales. These components of EQ-i:YV measure one's general feeling of contentment and overall outlook on life. High scores on these components indicate a positive outlook that can help bolster oneself and those around. The results indicate an effective use of optimism

to help maintain a positive attitude. This characteristic is usually beneficial in handling difficult or stressful situations

Optimism. The results indicate an effective use of optimism to help maintain a positive attitude. This characteristic is usually beneficial in handling difficult or stressful situations.

Happiness The responses to this scale indicate a person who feels generally satisfied with life. Students who show happiness probably have a happy and pleasant disposition that will help maintain, or perhaps even promote, positive feelings in those around him. A positive atmosphere can help lift spirits and improve overall functioning/performance.

Contains two validity indicators--**The Positive Impression Scale**, which measures the extent to which an individual is trying to present himself or herself in an overly positive light and **The Inconsistency Index**, which helps detect individuals who are responding haphazardly or in an inconsistent way.

This instrument can be used in clinical settings to assess an individual's general degree of emotional intelligence, potential for emotional health, and present psychological well-being, as well as to help establish clear therapeutic goals and evaluate the success of a therapy or intervention program.

It is ideal for use in educational settings to help school psychologists and professionals identify students whose inability to adequately cope with school demands could lead to dropping out of school and/or the development of emotional and behavioural problems.

Dimension of Emotional Intelligence (EI)

A. Self-regulations

"Self-regulation (or self-regulated learning) refers to learning that results from a student's self-generated thought and behaviors that are systematic oriented toward the attainment of their learning goals" (Schunk & Zimmerman, 2003, p.59).

Self-regulation or self-management is the second of Goleman's core competencies. The concept of self-management is through the ability to remain calm during provocative or conflict situation, while keeping defensiveness to a minimum and ultimately renovating rationality (Wolmarans & Martins, 2001). Self-regulation progresses primarily from social source and changes to individual sources in a sequence of levels (Schunk & Zimmerman, 2003). According to Schunk & Zimmerman, (2003) self-regulation would encourage people to take a more powerful role on their thoughts, emotions, and performances.

B. Self awareness

Self-awareness is the most crucial competency associated with work place emotional intelligence. Grayson, (2013) defined self-awareness as the ability to recognize one's feelings, to differentiate between them, to know what one is feeling and why, and to know what caused the feelings. Goleman (1998) defined emotional self-awareness as a way of identifying a person emotions and how it could effects. Yeung (2009) stated that the first step of becoming an emotionally intelligent is to become as self-aware as possible. Yeung (2009) also argued that if emotional intelligence were a journey, then self-awareness would be the skill of map reading.

C. Self-motivation

Goleman (1995) defined that emotional self-motivation involves the ability of controlling the emotional tendencies that facilitate in other to reach one's goals. Self-motivation also refers to the abilities to set goals and create an arduous, and also to remain focused and positive by any setbacks that may occur during setting goals. Self-motivation is assurances would involve in every day action which could also committed to any particular cause. Wolmrans & Martins, (2001) suggested that one way that are founded on self-motivations is taking responsibility for a person successes and failures.

D. Social skill (relationship management)

Social skills refer to a person's talent in managing relationship with others and building systems also called people skills. The set of social skills includes respect for others, mutual regard, commitment, openness, tolerance, empathy, negotiation, communication etc. (Schuetz, 2011). It involves the ability of meeting each other's needs, relating to each other over time and exchanging information about one feeling, thought and ideas. Others qualities, social skills are effective in leading change, persuading others, building and leading teams (Goleman 1995). Social interaction also results in many advantages. It gives confidence and social acceptance. It can help managers in many ways. It can help do many things which cannot be completed alone, for example; getting support from a team or completing a project (Pettry, 2006).

E. Job Performances

"Job performance is the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioural episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period of time. Other than that, it is also an individual output in terms of Jex (2002) defined job performance as all behaviors that employees engage at work. Goleman (2005) asserted that EI enhance performance and effectiveness of individuals. Scullen, Mount & Goff, (2000) stated that job performance act as an important concept in organizational practice and research. It also acts as the main role in most personnel decisions such as merit-based payment, promotion and retention of employees by enabling people to nurture positive relationships at work, work effectively in teams, and build social capital. Work performance often depends on the support, advice, and other resources provided by others (Seibert, Kraimer & Liden, 2001). Carmeli (2003) stressed that employees with a high level of intelligence can manage their emotions in terms of retaining a positive mental state which can lead to improved job performance.

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction (JS) is “a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences” (Locke, 1969; 1976). It is the perception of the employee on how well the things are provided that is considered as important. In the discipline of organizational behavior, JS is one of the most crucial and frequently studied constructs. Individuals with positive feelings about their jobs show high levels of job satisfaction; while an individual with negative feelings about his/her job shows low level of job satisfaction. Studies show that jobs with training, variety, independence and autonomy satisfy the majority of employees (Damenpour, 1991).

JS is simply an attitude with three generally accepted dimensions. Firstly, how the employee feels emotionally with regard to the job and the level to which the job provides the individual with interesting tasks, learning possibilities and empowerment. The content of the work itself is the most significant factor affecting job satisfaction. A previous survey done by Price Water house Coopers in 2008 uncovered that career development was most important to young employees (cited in Leaf & Ryan, 2010).

JS is often established on the basis of relationship between work output and the individual expectations. The expectations may be in the form of financial remuneration or appreciation from the superiors or in the form of advancement in the organization. Pay is the pivotal variable that often comes up when JS is discussed (Leaf & Ryan, 2010). For people who are at the start of their career, pay does correlate with job satisfaction and overall happiness. This situation takes an overturn when an individual attains a stage of comfortable living.

While there is no significant difference between males and females when it comes to analytical skills, problem solving, competitiveness, optimism and other intellectual abilities, different groups report different scores on some elements of JS. Kifle and Desta (2012) show that females are more satisfied with the social networking they encounter inside the organization. However, males are motivated by career progress, responsibilities and working hours. Petrides and Furnham (2006) found that females experience less perceived control on their work as they progress. This in turn leads to less organizational commitment and less JS. Onuoha and Segun-Martins (2013) did their study on married working women. They found a positive correlation between JS and EI.

One of the reasons of women’s more contended attitudes is that they stress more on their role as home-makers relatively and extend pleasure from the responsibilities fulfilled at home front (Veroff, Douvan, & Kulka, 1981). A working woman instead of comparing herself with the similar level male employee in the organization, her comparison is with the other women. Hence, she expects less as compared to her male counterpart. As per Clark (1997), the disparity between males and females starts decreasing with the years of experience and qualifications. It is also reduced with age. Younger females have more expectations as compared to older females. On the other hand, females report that they need work-life balance to meet the demands of their homes while males ask for more money (Leaf & Ryan, 2010).

It is worthy to note that this study is a continuation of another two papers (El-Badawy & Sadek, in review; El-Badawy, Srivastava, & Sadek, 2014). The first paper investigated EI, JS

and and India. It found significant positive relationship between EI and JS. It was concluded that different cultural and demographic variables need to be explored in terms of their effect on EI and JS. Therefore, the purpose of this paper was formed. First, the effects of gender and age on EI, JS and the relationship between EI and JS were investigated. Second, the impact of EI on JS among academicians in higher education institutions of Egypt was tested.

Job Satisfaction is also depend gender and age also:-

Job Satisfaction and Gender

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Kifle and Desta (2012) investigated the difference in JS among persons who completed their PhD at Australia's Group of Eight (Go8) universities. JS was not dependent on gender, despite that the author controlled the variables like age, employment status and family type/living arrangement. For those with statistically accepted differences, males are more contented than females with the basic sphere of JS that includes satisfaction with hours worked, satisfaction with prospect for career advancement and satisfaction with workload. Females are satisfied with another facet that takes account of contributing to the society and conducting relationships with fellow employees.

Job Satisfaction and Age

Although demographic variables play a significant role in the studies related to JS, results were often conflicting. As per Hertzberg et al. (1957), when an employee starts his/her job, the enthusiasm and drive to perform is on the higher side and start decreasing in the following years. However, older employees tend to be more satisfied with their jobs as compared to younger ones. The survey conducted by Morello (2010) in Washington Post shows that, for all ages, only 45 percent of the respondents marked 4-5 on a scale of 5 indicating a positive response to JS. This was the lowest percentage ever encountered showing how employees are dissatisfied in their work. Gallup-Healthways well-being index reported 87.5 percent of Americans are happy with their jobs. Older employees have the maximum level of JS with approximately 95 percent (Mendes, 2011). The reasons proposed for such results were a lucrative package, a satisfying career, expertise and stability desired in a particular age.

On the other hand, Onuoha and Segun-Martins (2013) found a negative relationship between age and JS. The researchers justify the results saying that older employees may have lost their physical skills so they make mistakes; they have lower productivity and consequently lose satisfaction with work. They also mentioned that culture plays a larger part in the findings. The study was conducted in Nigeria where the dependency rate of adults is high due to unemployment. Hence, the working population feels more stress and the result is high dissatisfaction rate. More recently, a report published by the Conference Board research firm found that average Americans are overall satisfied with their jobs; however, they are not happy (2014). The employees reported that communication, interest in job tasks and recognition are the most important determinants of JS and it is the responsibility of the employer to ensure the availability of such elements. It is believed that for employers, in a tight market and suffering economies, should put JS as a high priority to attract and retain the qualified

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research highlights the importance of emotional intelligence. It appears that the four domains

(self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills) of emotional intelligence have a greater impact on teachers' job performance. In order to sustain high performance and competitive advantage, emotional

intelligence should be developed and improved through a systematic and consistent approach (Perkins, 1995; Bar-On, 1997; Cooper & Sawaf, 1997; Cherniss & Goleman, 1998; Goleman, 1998). Therefore, it is recommended that organizations develop training programs in improving emotional competencies of their managers and workers in the organization. Organizations should recognize the significant role of emotional intelligence in developing human capital that leads to a high-performing workforce.

The Emotional Intelligence is a construct that still requires research and deepening, and according to the results of some researches done in the same subject show its importance within the study of social and intellectual human competence.

So we believe that it is useful and interesting to consider how important the Emotional Intelligence is for academic performance.

Finally, it might be helpful to keep in mind that emotional intelligence comprises a large set of abilities that have been studied by psychologists for many years. Thus, another way to measure emotional intelligence or competence is through tests of specific abilities.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that management should include some faculty training programs in order to enhance their emotional intelligence based on their job satisfaction. Such programs will assist the faculties in developing better empathic and interpersonal relations with their peers, administrators, understanding students unique needs and hence in better management of their classes. Such faculty education programs should provide instruction for novice teachers also so as to increase their understanding and knowledge of emotional intelligence, methods, and programs that might be employed in the teaching pedagogy resulting in enhanced effectiveness. The study has not included the impact of gender, age, and experience on emotional intelligence. Further research can be carried out to examine the impact of these variables as moderating variables.

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